
Studies of the influence of culverts on the upper structure of the track on the sections of high-speed and high-speed train traffic

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Abstract: In this article, the analysis of the culvert capacity of the pipe is carried out and, based on the data obtained, the effect on the state of the path is investigated.

Keywords: Pipes, rails, irregularities, measurements, indicator, filling of pipes experimental section.

Introduction. The durability of rails, the comfort of high-speed and high-speed trains, and the wear of rolling stock are largely related to the condition of culverts. During the movement of trains, either local or extended irregularities occur on the surface of the rails (undulating deformation of the rails). According to the accepted classification of defects of rails NTD CP-2-93, the most significant are:

- undulating deformation of the rail head (defect 40);
- crumpling and vertical wear of the head (defects 41.1-2);
- lateral wear of the head in excess of the available standards (defect 44).

These irregularities appear in places where there are culverts. Because the changes in the pipe capacity are very poorly pushed into the VSP.

In this article, the local irregularities of the rolling surface of the rail head arising in the sections of high-speed and high-speed train traffic of JSC "Uzbekistan Temir Yullari" are considered. At the same time, the track measuring car No. 106 of the track management is measured and evaluated[1.2.3].

To study the presence of a culvert randomly within the Tashkent - Samarkand line, three experimental sites were assigned, the characteristics of which are given in Table1.

In accordance with the developed research methodology, at the first stage, the

presence of pipes in the experimental sites is assessed. Subsequently, it is planned to study the possible causes of the development of pipe flooding to develop recommendations for elimination and prevention.

For the initial assessment of the VSP at the experimental sites, the results of track measurements by track measuring car No. 106 dated September 10, 2022 were used[7.8.9].

The main indicators of the VSP condition at the experimental sites by the presence and filling of culverts are presented in Table 1.

№	Numbers of experimental plots	Number of culverts, pcs.	Pipe throughput as a percentage in 3 years		
			2020	2021	2022
1	Tashkent-Gulistan	168	89%	87%	86%
2	Gulistan-Jizzakh	149	78%	77%	74%
3	Jizzakh- Samarkand	114	88%	84%	78%

Based on the results of the study, the following drawing was drawn up (Fig. 1) for a culvert under a railway track.

Defects of culverts: 1 – stagnation of water at the ends of the pipe; 2 – local destruction of the fortifications of the slopes; 3 – silting of the pipe; 4 – violation of the tightness of the joints; 5 – separation of the links; 6 – partial destruction of the heads. Defects on the coating caused by the condition of culverts: 7 – trackage; 8 – potholes; 9 – waves; 10 – subsidence; 11 – depths; 12 – opening of the pipe body[4.5].

The results of systematization are presented in the study of the presence of a culvert randomly within the Tashkent - Samarkand line, three experimental sites were assigned, the characteristics of which are given in Table 2.

№	Hole Type	Number of fixed defects												Number of pipes	Number of observations
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
1)	round	8	0	6	0	0	13	0	0	0	4	0	0	25	13
2)	rectangular	6	0	10	0	0	17	0	0	0	9	0	0	20	17
3)	round rectangular	10	0	5	0	0	9	0	0	0	7	0	0	16	10

Conclusions. The technical condition is the main characteristic of the ability of the pipes to provide a normal operating mode associated with the safe passage of trains with set speeds and uninterrupted passage of the watercourse through the body of the embankment. The main indicators of the technical condition are considered to be the actual bearing capacity of the pipe elements, as well as the degree of development of various violations of hydraulic and other functions of the structures. In real conditions, the current technical condition of artificial structures operated on railways is characterized by the presence of signs limiting the possibility of increasing the axial and linear loads of freight cars. This, in turn, is a deterrent to increasing the

capacity of railway sections. In accordance, further scientific research is necessary to solve the problem of improving the operational reliability of culverts.

List of literature:

1. Abdualiyev Elyorbek Begaliyevich, Mirzahidova Ozoda Mirzabdulayebna, and Khamidov Mahsud Kamolovich. "STUDIES OF THE MODE OF OPERATION OF CULVERTS ON RAILWAY LINES." BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI (2022): 307-310.
2. Абдуалиев Элёрбек Бегалиевич; Махамаджанов Шухрат Шавкатович, Аvezмурат Бекмуратович Ембергенов. "ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ РЕЖИМА РАБОТЫ ВОДОПРОПУСКНЫХ ТРУБ НА ЖЕЛЕЗНОДОРОЖНЫХ ЛИНИЯХ АО «ЎЗБЕКИСТАН ТЕМИР ЙЎЛЛАРИ»." BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI 2.1 (2022): 411-415.
3. Rustamovich, Khalfin G., and Purtseladze I. Borisovna. "Use of a System for Determining the State of a Non-jointed Track to Ensure the Safety of Train Traffic." JournalNX, vol. 7, no. 05, 2021, pp. 242-245, doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/U3A2F.
4. Abdualiyev, Elyorbek Begaliyevich, and Auezmurat Bekmuratovich Embergenov. "HYDRAULIC CALCULATIONS OF CULVERTS ON THE HIGH-SPEED SECTION OF THE TASHKENT-SIRDARYA RAILWAY LINE." Academic research in educational sciences 2.4 (2021): 1964-1968.
5. Abdualiyev, Elyorbek Begaliyevich, Movjuda Mikhaliyovna Mirkhanova, and Shukhrat Shavkatovich Makhamadjonov. "CONDITION OF CULVERTS ON THE HIGH-SPEED SECTION OF THE TASHKENT-SYRDARYA RAILWAY LINE." Academic research in educational sciences 2.2 (2021): 1096-1101.